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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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Questioning the coming age of multimodal research infrastructure

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Introduction

The last 20 years has been one of revolution for scholarly information infrastructure and, as a result, the way in which we think about the scholarly record has drastically changed. At the turn of the millennium collecting complete, well-structured data for scholarly records of individual researchers was still aspirational. Even with the rise of the internet and of data sources such as Web of Science and Scopus in the 2000s, many academics did not have good quality lists of their own research careers which were not principally paper based. The scholarly record was difficult to obtain, brittle, difficult to search, hard to validate and almost impossible to interrogate at scale. Twenty years later and persistent identifier infrastructure is pervasive, the core of the scholarly record is increasingly openly available, and the research community is able to build on a firm foundation.

And yet, in the face of all this progress, innovation in scholarly information appears to be slowing. CRIS systems are widespread; bibliometrics, scientometrics and research on research are all growing fields; but we do not see research decisionmakers pushing for more as once they did. It could be that twenty years ago the need was more urgent as there was more of a void; it could be that the status quo is comfortable. But, this lull in activity may have more pernicious undertones: a) complacency or fatigue – feeling that we already have enough metrics and indicators that little can be added by adding more – indeed, less may be more! b) investment saturation – many have invested considerably in data, infrastructure, analysts and it may be difficult at this point to justify further funding; c) fear of responsible evaluation – decision makers may be concerned that any of use of data may be frowned upon as they don't fully understand the details of responsible evaluation.

While any (or all) of these factors may play a role, we argue that we are in the calm before the storm and that a new wave of innovation is coming. There are two core reasons for our optimism: firstly, that we see more and more uses of machine learning and artificial intelligence in the software that we are seeing released to support researchers; secondly, we believe that the highly multimodal nature of research is not served well by current solutions that this is an important next step in improving both experience of all participants in the scholarly ecosystem.

The rise of multimodality

Modern research is intrinsically multimodal. What we mean by that statement is that essentially all aspects of the modern research ecosystem rely on stitching together multiple data sources, mixed methods, and different perspectives. The move away from the era of the lone genius and into an era of team research has been recognised for some time, but embracing this development is a slower process since so much of our cultural norms and institutions are oriented around this well-established historic mode. This isn't simply a change in culture to reflect modern sensibility. Multimodality is required to address the research problems that we face today, problems that have simply grown to large and complex to be progressed by individualistic approaches or that are so tied to societal, environmental, or political issues that large-scale engagement is itself a key part of the research process and required for successful translation to impact.

We see multimodality manifesting in many forms across the research ecosystem: multimodal funding – where companies partner with state funders or crowd funders support research; multimodal collaboration – where research institutions engage with different partners, who are closer to the impact that must be made and citizen scientists become part of massive experiments; multimodal careers – where intelligent individuals pass more seamlessly between research, industry, policy and third-sector jobs; and, multimodal organisations – who aim to progress research and contribute their findings back into the public domain for the good of all. Yet, while all these modes contribute to a more vibrant and interesting research ecosystem, improving the diversity of the perspectives that can be brought to bear on solving and translating research problems to have greater impact, they also pose several problems for the research infrastructure community.

The scholarly record that we perceived at the turn of the millennium is not the scholarly record of today. While journal articles, conference proceedings and books currently remain the atom of scholarly communication, how long will this remain the case? We already see challenges with the speed of peer review processes (Herbert et al., 2015; Johansson & Sadari, 2020); of how we handle affiliations and contributions (Allen et al., 2014; Porter, 2022); of how we evaluate and trace back contributions to funders and innovators (Fecher et al., 2015; Ravenscroft et al., 2017; Bornmann, 2017; D. Hook, 2020); and of how we handle research integrity in an ever more complex environment (McIntosh, 2021; Sumner et al., 2022). These challenges will get worse.

Discussion

While, in the last 20 years, we have tamed the scholarly record, we should not be complacent. As research becomes more multimodal, the scholarly record will need morph into something new. The systems that currently contain it will not be fit for purposes; the ways in which we capture, record, and communicate scholarship will change. The process of change has already begun, but are we thinking radically enough about the mechanisms and systems that we will need to put in place in this emergent world?

It is not just the systems of storing and reporting that will need to change, but also the way that we expect to search, interrogate, and evaluate. Digital Science has spent the last few years considering these challenges (D. W. Hook et al., 2018; D. W. Hook & Porter, 2021; Herzog et al., 2020; Porter & Hook, 2022), designing systems that begin a journey beyond publications and citations. And yet, a publication-focus remains at the core of the analyses that academics, administrators, and policy makers continue to use to support their stakeholders. Are we about

to see another revolution or will research be held back by infrastructures that no longer fit our needs, as was the case in 2000? In either case, a new age of innovation is almost certainly just around the corner, the only question will be whether our community leads or lags.

Conflict of interest

The co-authors are current employees of Digital Science, the owner and provider of Altmetric, Dimensions, Figshare, Overleaf, Readcube/Papers, Ripeta and Symplectic Elements.

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